

building-integrated user-
empowered flexibility trading

Deliverable D8.3: 1st report on dissemination, communication and clustering activities and results

WP8 – Dissemination and Communication

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PUBLIC

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Document Section	Author(s)	Reviewer(s)
All sections	Matthias Strobbe (imec) with contributions from all project partners	Artur Andrzejewski (ENEA), Josep Mayos (CIMNE)

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the communication, dissemination, and clustering activities carried out by the BlueBird project during its first 18 months. These activities are essential to ensure the visibility of the project, promote awareness and uptake of its results, and maximize its scientific, societal, and market impact. The report assesses progress against the communication and dissemination strategy defined in D8.2 and provides an overview of achievements across all major dissemination channels, including the project website, social media, publications, events, and collaboration with other European initiatives and stakeholder networks.

During the reporting period, BlueBird established a solid communication presence through its project website, LinkedIn channel and Zenodo community. A broad portfolio of dissemination materials was developed, including flyers, posters, infographics, press releases, and a first project white paper. Scientific dissemination activities have taken off well, with four publications already published or accepted and several additional papers under review or in preparation. BlueBird has been very active in conferences, workshops, and exhibitions, with presentations and booths at a wide range of academic, industrial, and policy-oriented events.

In parallel, BlueBird has invested significant effort in community and ecosystem building activities. The project joined the Smart Energy Cluster, which currently brings together more than 40 European projects working on smart energy services, flexibility, and consumer engagement. A.o. through this network, BlueBird established collaborations with several complementary Horizon Europe projects, including CELINE, EVELIXIA, STUNNED, and ENTRANCE. Furthermore, BlueBird actively contributes to the BRIDGE initiative through participation in working groups addressing user engagement and business models.

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I. INTRODUCTION

I.1. Purpose and organization of the document

This deliverable describes the communication and dissemination activities carried out by the BlueBird project partners during the first 18 months of the project. These activities have as goal to ensure a high visibility of the BlueBird innovations and to maximize their adoption and impact.

The document is structured according to the main communication and dissemination channels defined in D8.2:

- Website
- Social media (LinkedIn)
- Newsletters & Press Releases
- Flyers and Posters
- Videos
- Scientific Publications
- Participation in (Industry Oriented) events, Workshops and Conferences
- White papers
- Public events organized by BlueBird
- Outreach to stakeholders

The results from the communication and dissemination activities in the second half of the project (M19-M36) will be reported in *D8.4 - 2nd report on dissemination, communication and clustering activities and results* (M36).

I.2. Structure of the document

The rest of the document is structured as follows:

- Section 2: Overview of all performed communication and dissemination activities during the first 18 months of the project.
- Section 3: Overview of performed activities related to engagement with other EU projects, EU initiatives and EU level stakeholders.
- Section 4: Conclusion.

II. COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

The partners in BlueBird are dedicated to engaging relevant stakeholders, amplifying the reach of dissemination and exploitation efforts, and maximising the project's impact. This commitment is aligned with the 6 main target audiences identified in [deliverable D8.2](#).

The success of the communication and dissemination actions to promote the project results is measured with a number of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) as defined in the project proposal. The KPIs and their current status are listed below for each communication & dissemination channel.

II.1. Website

KPI descripton	Target KPI Value	Status M18
Website visits & updates	2 updates per month, 5000+ visitors/year	535 unique visitors, 10000+ page views, regular updates

The public project website is available on <https://bluebird-project.eu> and is an important communication tool for the project. The website features the main objectives of the project, the overall architecture and methodology, detailed descriptions of the 7 pilots, an overview of the consortium, a news section and a link to our [Zenodo community](#) where all public project results are uploaded. This Zenodo community is also part of the [EU Open Research Repository](#), to further increase the visibility and impact of our project's results.

As BlueBird focuses on the design and implementation of open solutions, most deliverables have been publicly released on Zenodo. Furthermore, the BlueBird Zenodo community currently contains a first project white paper, 3 scientific publications, several event presentations, 2 project posters and 2 project flyers. These public results received until now 854 views and 653 downloads.

The project website is updated regularly, featuring all LinkedIn posts (see section II.2. in the news section, and with regular additions to the pilot description and project methodology pages.

Figure 1. BlueBird website

Figure 2. BlueBird Zenodo community

We use Google Analytics to get insight in the usage of the BlueBird website. Over a period of about 15 months (since the website is live, end of March 2025), about 535 unique visitors visited the website, for a total of 1000+ sessions and 10000+ page views. Most visitors reached the site directly.

Figure 3. Website usage insights via Google Analytics

The number of visits to the website up to now is lower than the targeted 5000 visitors per year. Once more results—including those from the pilot validations—become available, and we can showcase these results at events and in publications, we hope that visitor numbers will continue to rise. Nevertheless, achieving this KPI might not be possible, and the KPI target was likely too ambitious. We also believe it is easier to reach relevant stakeholders through our LinkedIn page (see section II.2.).

II.2. LinkedIn

KPI description	Target KPI Value	Status M18
LinkedIn	500+ followers, 26 posts/year (2/month)	216 followers, 31 posts

Social media are used to raise awareness on project results, pilot validations, project events and publications. [LinkedIn](#) is used as main social media channel as it gives the opportunity of enhancing two-way communication with well-defined professional groups of stakeholders.

Figure 4. BlueBird LinkedIn page

In the project proposal also X (Formerly Twitter) was mentioned as social media channel to be used, but due to controversy surrounding X and concerns related to the actions and public statements of its owner, we have decided not to use X as a communication channel for our project, as it does not align with the openness, inclusivity, and responsible engagement values that our project pursues.

Similar to the website, we engaged to provide regular posts on LinkedIn, about 2 per month. All partners contribute by writing articles on a monthly rotating basis, supplemented by updates on event participations, publications, pilot deployment updates, etc. At M18 we have published 31 posts (with several additional

posts planned), very close to this target. We expect to further increase the update rate during the second half of the project when more concrete project results and pilot validations become available.

In terms of reach, we aim to reach over 500 followers for our project’s LinkedIn page by the end of the project. We are now at 216 followers, which is not far off from 50% of this KPI, halfway through the project. We hope to achieve this KPI by continuing to post regular updates about our project and by mentioning the LinkedIn page as much as possible in our public dissemination activities (presentations, posters, etc.).

Figure 5. LinkedIn Impressions metric for the past 12 months

Furthermore, the different posts on our LinkedIn page generated during the past 12 months 13895 impressions (number of times a post was shown on LinkedIn), reached 6312 LinkedIn members (number of distinct members that saw a post), and received 413 reactions (likes), as shown on Figure 5.

II.3. Newsletters & Press Releases

KPI description	Target KPI Value	Status
Press releases or newsletters	2 per year (6 in total)	2 press releases at M1 and M13

Two electronic press releases were published until now:

- A first one was published at the start of the project on the [project website](#) and on the websites of several partners, e.g., from the [University of Stuttgart](#), highlighting the overall goals of the project, an introduction to the 7 pilot sites in 5 different countries, and BlueBird’s intention to compile a package of lessons learned and actionable recommendations to ensure a long-term impact and replicability of the project.
- After project year 1, a second press release was published on the [project website](#) and [LinkedIn page](#), highlighting the main achievements during the first 12 months of the project including the

set-up and activation of the pilot sites, the creation of a comprehensive portfolio of use cases that steer the development of the BlueBird reference architecture and flexibility services, the research on acceptance and adoption of demand response services by end users, and a lookout on project year 2 where the focus is more on deployment, validation, and impact assessment.

We will continue to give regular updates on the project progress and results, mainly via the project website and LinkedIn page.

II.4. Flyers / Posters / Infographics

KPI description	Target KPI Value	Status
Posters and flyers	3 of each	2 posters and 2 flyers published

BlueBird Context

To achieve the EU's Green Deal and sustainability targets, its power grid has seen a drastic increase in renewable energy resources. This causes balancing the electricity supply and demand to be ever more challenging and calls for increased flexibility in the electricity system. Hence, flexibility schemes lie at the core of the EU's holy grail to realize the required energy transition.

BlueBird focuses on unlocking such energy flexibility from buildings, and thus will deliver a comprehensive and validated toolset, to fully allow competitive adoption of buildings as energy flexibility assets. BlueBird's toolset will build on standard ontologies to supporting a smooth integration of services towards energy market players (i.e. TSO, DSO, aggregators) while maximally aligning with end-user's (i.e. building managers, occupants) requirements and acceptance criteria.

BlueBird Objectives

The project has 5 key objectives:

- Provide multi-carrier flexibility services for buildings, integrating energy and non-energy carriers, empowering end-users with control;
- Facilitate the flexibility trading between buildings and the energy market stakeholders;
- Evaluate BlueBird in 7 demonstrators with residential, public, commercial, office and industrial buildings;
- Maximize adoption based on (1) business models and successful value networks, and (2) a set of feasibility studies for on-site storage and renewables;
- Deliver a highly replicable, standardized, benefit-demonstrated Replicability Package.

BlueBird Business Cases

BlueBird has defined a wide range of targeted high-level services that form the core drivers for the technical developments. These services have been identified through a detailed analysis of 7 business cases across Europe, covering 24 use cases. Below, we summarize the business cases in terms of the available equipment, involved stakeholders, and how flexibility will be used.

To realize these services, BlueBird will deliver a toolset of hierarchical predictive control software, comprising a Trading Manager (to unlock flexibility and allow participation in energy markets), a Flexibility Manager (to jointly control assets at the building level), and interaction tools (to empower users and building managers).

#1 Karno
Karno (a Belgian zero-carbon district heating developer) will upgrade its 4th generation low-temperature (35 °C) network to improve integration in the electrical power grid. This includes (1) increasing flexibility by adapting to user behavior; (2) leveraging additional flex from storage and local PV; and (3) expanding the heating network.

#2 AMB
The metropolitan area of Barcelona (AMB) aims to leverage flexibility from public building systems (heat pumps for heating and/or cooling, gas-based heating) and EV chargers, to (1) optimize self-consumption of local PV and solar thermal, and/or (2) enable participation to the Iberian electricity markets (e.g. TOU-based).

#3 WeSmart
As an energy aggregator, WeSmart wants to leverage EMS-based control within the energy community at the Tour & Taxis site in Brussels, Belgium. This will encompass (1) real-time data acquisition from end users' smart meters, EV chargers and 10k rooftop PV panels, (2) recommendation-based DR from end users, and (3) validating economic viability accounting for user behavior.

#4 Enea Office
The Polish power company Enes will enable dynamic management of its office building's cooling and heating system, fed by a municipal heating grid. This will encompass (1) predictive monitoring and control of the office's and social rooms' thermostats, and (2) providing users with thermostat settings accounting for their comfort.

#5 Enea Grid
As a 2nd case for Enea, it will maximally exploit flexibility of a high/medium voltage power station's cooling and heating, with minimal impact on comfort and assuring safety of technical staff. BlueBird will realize (1) non-intrusive monitoring and AI-based predictive control, and (2) dynamic heating and cooling management to unlock flexibility.

#6 EK
The Austrian flexibility aggregator and service provider Energie Kompass will market Wasserband Südliches Burgenland's water works building's battery and operational flex. This will entail (1) upgrading the automation system of the water tanks, (2) optimizing its operation and scheduling exploiting the tanks as energy storage, and (3) improving VPP capability and functionality.

#7 EWH
EWH as a vertically integrated electricity supplier/DSO, generates electricity from local renewables and manages supply EWH will exploit BlueBird technology to better manage its largest customers (i.e., hotels) to (1) identify and forecast their load and flexibility, and subsequently, (2) turn the hotels into smart-grid-ready buildings.

Partners

inetum, Cimne, wesmart, imtec, PSNC, KARNO, Enea, AMB, EWH, TERGA, BPIE, Energie Kompass, AIT

For more information, please follow us on [LinkedIn.com/company/bluebird-project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/bluebird-project) or bluebird-project.eu

The BlueBird project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101192452.

Figure 6. First BlueBird flyer

Flyers and posters are used to communicate the main goals and outcomes from the project on scientific and industrial conferences, workshops, fairs and other types of events.

During the first months of the project a flyer was created (Figure 6), highlighting the project context and key objectives, the different partners, and the 7 pilot environments, and made available to all project partners in both English and French. This flyer was distributed on several events, including the [BRIDGE General Assembly of March 25-26 2025](#), [Smart City Expo 2025](#) (November 3-5 2025) and pilot workshops.

Figure 7. Distribution of the BlueBird flyer on BRIDGE General Assembly - March 26 2025

In October 2025 a first project poster was created to present the project on the InEEs final conference in Brussels (October 15 2025).

Figure 8. Presentation of BlueBird poster on the InEEs final conference - October 15 2025

More recently a new flyer and poster were created for the [ECEEE summer study event](#) (June 1-6, 2026) where BPIE presented BlueBird (see section II.9. All posters and flyers can be downloaded from the [BlueBird Zenodo community](#).

Furthermore, several infographics were developed to serve both online and printed formats, offering an overview of the BlueBird architecture, the user empowerment approach, the use case system encompassing all pilot use cases, the regulatory framework analysis, and the business modelling methodology. These infographics are used on the website ([project overview page](#)) and are available for use in posters and flyers (e.g. the architecture infographic was used in the project poster).

II.5. Videos

KPI descripton	Target KPI Value	Status
Project videos	At least 3 with 1500+ views each	First video will be created in Q4 2026

Project videos are considered an important communication and dissemination tool to maximise the impact of the project, and we believe we can create the most impact by showcasing tangible results from the seven project pilots.

To ensure that these pilot videos provide meaningful and credible insights, their production is planned for the second half of the project, when we have results on the deployment and validation of the BlueBird modules on site. A first video is planned to be created for the 2 ENEA pilots in Poland during the plenary meeting there later this year.

II.6. Scientific Publications

KPI descripton	Target KPI Value	Status
Scientific publications in journals and proceedings of academic conferences and workshops.	At least 8	3 published, 1 paper accepted, several papers under review or in preparation

Scientific publications, following an open-access policy as per EC guidelines, are an important outcome of the BlueBird project, and a key exploitable result, mainly for the universities and research institutes involved. At month 18 we have 3 project papers presented and published:

- Judit Kockat, “Implementing EU building, energy and market rules for building-level flexibility: insights from six pilot contexts”, in proceedings of the ECEEE 2026 Summer Study, Lac d’Ailette, France, 1-6 June 2026.
- Giuseppe Gabriele, Fabio Pavirani, Seyed Soroush Karimi Madahi, Chris Develder, “Forecasting What Matters: Decision-Focused RL for Controlled EV Charging with Unknown Departure Times”, in proceedings of ACM e-Energy 2026, Banff, Canada, June 22-26 2026.
- Kyril Kaufmann, Georgios Tsaousaoglou, “The Cost-Emissions Trade-off Under Network Constraints”, in proceedings of the International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM26), Trondheim, Norway, June 22-24 2026.

A fourth paper which focuses a.o. on the flexibility user study from WP4, has recently been accepted for the International Conference Applied Psychology in Florence, Italy (21-25 July 2026).

Several additional journal and conference papers are currently under review or in preparation. With the expected increase of more tangible results during the second half of the project, we expect that we will exceed the target KPI value.

II.7. Participation in Events, Workshops & Conferences

KPI descripton	Target KPI Value	Status
Participation in industry-oriented events and exhibitions	At least 3 per year (9 in total)	15

This category includes presentations and contributions from BlueBird to events, workshops, panels, fairs and conferences, including both industry and academic focused events, without an actual publication. Opportunities for contributions to these kind of events are typically discussed during the monthly project status calls and the physical plenary meetings.

We were quite active in the first 18 months in disseminating the goals and ongoing research activities of BlueBird in a broad range of events. Almost all activities have been promoted via a post on the BlueBird LinkedIn page and a news article on the BlueBird website:

- 03/04/2025: [Presentation of the BlueBird project](#) in the context of a talk about the adoption of smart thermostats at the 2025 SmartGreens Conference, with both researchers and practioneers from 13 countries across the EU and across the world.
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* ±30 conference participants, mostly researchers, some industry stakeholders
- 16/04/2025: [Presentation of the BlueBird project](#) by Josep Mayos (CIMNE) on the 3rd Collaboration Workshop of the [Smart Energy Cluster](#), a dynamic network of 40+ EU projects, all working together to accelerate the clean energy transition across Europe.
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* ±30 people (academia & industry from Horizon Europe projects)
- 23/04/2025: [Invited talk](#) by prof. Chris Develder (imec) on the [Sustainable Electric Power Generation under EU Conditions workshop](#), highlighting a number of AI techniques that will be used, improved and validated in BlueBird to make buildings truly flexible assets.
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* ±30 people (mainly from academia)
- 16/06/2025: [Presentation of BlueBird](#) by Dr. Melanie Heck (University of Stuttgart) on the [19th Symposium and Summer School on Service-Oriented Computing](#) (SummerSoc 2025) in Heraklion, Crete.
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* ±40 people (mainly academia, a few people from industry)
- 16/06/2025: Presentation by Dr. Celina Kacperski (University of Seeburg) at the [2025 International Conference of Environmental Psychology \(ICEP\)](#) showcasing research on the design of experimental field trials in the energy sector, building on insights from BlueBird and other Horizon initiatives.
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* ±40 people (mainly academia)
- 16/09/2025: Presentation by Dr. Mona Marie Bielig (University of Seeburg) at the international [Conference of the Social Psychology Section \(FGSP\)](#). She presented the "Total Error Framework" for experimental field trials in the energy transition, drawing from BlueBird and previous Horizon projects.
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* ±30 people (mainly academia)
- 19/09/2025: Presentation and contribution to panel by Dr. Mona Marie Bielig (University of Seeburg) at the [final conference](#) of the [Horizon Europe int:net project](#). In her talk, she emphasized from a social science perspective how technical systems can fail if human adoption and decision-making are not considered, and linked these insights to BlueBird, highlighting the importance of the social factor in understanding and navigating flexibility in energy systems.
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* ±60 people (policy, academia & industry)

- 15/10/2025: [Presentation of BlueBird](#) at the [final conference](#) of the [InEExS LIFE project](#) via a contribution to a panel discussion, a presentation showcasing BlueBird’s core concepts and pilot activities, a [poster presentation](#) (see Figure 8), and contribution to an interactive session to explore synergies between BlueBird and the business cases investigated within InEExS.
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* ±40 people (academia & industry from Horizon Europe projects)
- 4-6/11/2025: BlueBird was showcased at the CIMNE booth during the [Smart City Expo World Congress in Barcelona](#), one of the world’s leading events for urban innovation.
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* ±300 people (Public authorities, city representatives, industry and technology providers)
- 10/12/2025: The WeSmart pilot was presented during the [First Conference for the Citizen Energy Advisory Hub](#) event in Brussels.
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* ±230 people (policy and institutional stakeholders, academia experts, industrial stakeholders)
- 17/03/2026: Dr. Sonja Klingert (University of Stuttgart) introduced BlueBird to the audience of the [ECOEMPOWER conference](#) “Uniting People and Practices Driving One Stop Shops for Energy Communities” during an interactive panel discussion.
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* 25 scientists from the area of energy flexibility
- 24/04/2026: Bianca Weber (University of Seeburg) presented the BlueBird project at Austria’s [Lange Nacht der Forschung](#), one of Europe’s largest public science events via a booth and poster.
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* ±50-100 people (mainly end users)
- 19/05/2026: Presentation by Dr. Sonja Klingert (University of Stuttgart) at the [SmartGreens 2026 conference](#)
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* ±40 conference participants, mostly researchers, some industry stakeholders
- 26/06/2026: Presentation by Dr. Amira Dhorbani (WeSmart) on the [first Nexgen user webinar](#) with focus on energy-community management best practices.
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* ±50 practitioners in the energy communities sector (community managers, local authorities, housing cooperatives), with a mix of Belgium-based projects and prospects active in the EU energy transition all involved or interested in digital tools for energy sharing and community management.
- 29/06/2026: Presentation of the BlueBird project by Dr. Matthias Strobbe (imec) at the [Grid Services & Markets Conference \(GSM 2026\)](#), Lucerne, Switzerland
 - o *Stakeholders reached:* 30 people (mainly academia & industry)

Figure 9. Presentation by Melanie Heck on SummerSoc 2025.

Figure 10. Contribution by Mona Bielig to panel on final conference of int:net project.

Figure 11. BlueBird flyer at the CIMNE booth at Smart City Expo World Congress 2025.

Figure 12. BlueBird booth at the Lange Nacht der Forschung.

We achieved the associated project KPI already within the first half of the project. Of course, dissemination and promotion activities will continue throughout the second half of the project, and further visibility and impact is expected once more research results and pilot validation outcomes become available.

Some of the events on our radar in the upcoming months where we hope to be able to present BlueBird are the following:

- [Smart City Expo World Congress 2026](#) in Barcelona, Spain (November 3-5 2026): CIMNE will likely have again a booth on this event and via the [Smart Energy Cluster](#) we applied to present our project during a stage session together with 4 other Horizon projects.
- [Enlit Europe 2026](#) in Vienna, Austria (November 10-12 2026)
- [Sustainable Places 2026](#) in Luxembourg , Luxembourg (December 2-4 2026)
- [E.DSO 3rd FutureGrid Innovation Summit 2027](#) in Brussels, Belgium (February 11 2027)

- [SmartGreens 2027](#) in Rome, Italy (April 16-17 2027)
- [European Sustainable Energy Week \(EUSEW\) 2027](#) in Brussels, Belgium (June 2027): In 2027 we hope to be able to host a policy session on energy security, consumer empowerment and demand-side flexibility.

II.8. White papers

KPI descripton	Target KPI Value	Status
White papers	At least 4	1

Figure 13. White paper on the use of the InterConnect DSO Interface and Knowledge Engine.

In April 2026 a first project white paper was published detailing the work of *T5.1 – Implementation of standardized flexibility frameworks and interfaces*.

This white paper examines how the DSO Interface and Knowledge Engine, developed within the [EU Horizon 2020 InterConnect project](#) and now being adapted by the BlueBird project, enables standardized semantic communication of market prices and flexibility signals across heterogeneous energy systems.

The task and associated white paper was coordinated by Inetum, and complemented with contributions from PSNC. The paper can be found on our [Zenodo community](#).

II.9. Public events organized by BlueBird

KPI descriptor	Target KPI Value	Status
Public events organized by BlueBird in workshops at conferences	2	1 (ECEEE summer study event)
Final project conference in Brussels	1 (80+ participants)	Planned for M33 – M35

Implementation gaps

& national practices emerging to address them

Regulatory frameworks that reward capital investment more than operational flexibility spending push DSOs toward grid reinforcement, discouraging flexibility, thereby weakening local flexibility markets.

- Germany:** Enables market-based DSO flexibility procurement
- Housing and cooling plans and electricity grid plans are still treated separately, limiting their use as coordination tools for flexibility, electrification and congestion management.**
- Germany:** Municipalities have planning links future heat demand and infrastructure
- Restricted metering data access, complex procedures and narrow proximity rules prevent energy sharing and collective self-consumption from scaling beyond single buildings or small groups.**
- Belgium:** Brussels has implemented the energy-sharing regulator rules, though data exchange remains to be finalized
- Spain:** Collectives self-consumption is permitted up to two kilometers between energy community participants and their buildings.
- Unclear or administratively heavy licensing, settlement, aggregation and compensation rules limit household and community participation in flexibility markets.**
- Austria:** Citizens energy communities can apply for the aggregator market role
- Germany:** Expects a more advanced flexibility aggregation framework

EU-level policy recommendations

To realize the potential of smart grid-ready buildings as effective assets for energy flexibility, Member States should fully transpose and implement the relevant EU provisions from EPBD, EPBD, EED, and RED II, in a coordinated and easy framework that enables households, communities and energy providers to participate effectively. Besides, the Commission should consider, notably in setting the post-2030 framework on EED and RED II:

- Provide EU-level implementation support to align national provisions across the EPBD, RED II, EPBD and EED into a coherent pathway, from smart readiness to flexibility service delivery
- Clarify the interaction between clean energy communities (CEDs Art. 2, 15a), renewable energy communities (REC Art. 2), collective self-consumption (CES Art. 2), energy sharing (ESD Art. 2, 4, 15a) and aggregation (EPD Art. 2), including their roles, possible combinations and implications for market access, data access, settlement and value allocation
- Develop EU-level methodological guidance enabling DSOs, regulators and public authorities to compare flexibility procurement, demand response, storage, energy communities and building-side measures with conventional grid reinforcement, making the energy efficiency first principle and network planning provisions operational (RED Art. 17)
- Provide support under IED Article 25 to help municipalities, DSOs, heat network operators and national infrastructure areas low level heat planning – including electrification, thermal storage and cooling demand – in line with electricity demand, distribution grid capacity, renewable generation and flexibility potential

Directives

We reviewed selected provisions of the following Directives, focusing only on those relevant to demand-side flexibility in buildings.

Acronym	Common Name	Link	Transposition time
EMD	Energy Market Design Directive	Directive (EU) 2024/1711 and 2024/1814	17.01.2025, 17.07.2024
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive	Directive (EU) 2024/1275	01.01.2025, 28.05.2024
REDII	Renewable Energy Directive	Directive (EU) 2023/2413	01.07.2024, 21.05.2023
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive	Directive (EU) 2023/1791	11.10.2023

Technical Annex
The detailed analysis underlying this policy brief is provided in BlueBird Deliverable C71, 'Regulatory background for smart grid-ready buildings and the energy network', which analyses the implementation of relevant EU provisions across the BlueBird pilot countries and regions, available on <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/electricity/infrastructure/bluebird/>

Authors
Julia Kucera
With contributions from Larissa Mita-Dob, Helene Schibye and Veronique Viallet
BPIE is a leading independent think tank focused on achieving climate neutrality in buildings. Our vision is a net-zero carbon built environment, aligned with the ambition of the Paris Agreement, and in support of a fair and sustainable society. We provide data-driven and actionable policy analysis, advice, and implementation support to decision-makers in Europe and globally, specialists.

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Design
Catherine Perry c.perry@bpi.eu

From Passive to Active:
How the EU and Member States enable buildings' demand side flexibility for a more resilient, renewable energy system

The need for demand-side energy flexibility from buildings

Buildings can play an active role in the energy system by providing demand-side flexibility. By shifting, reducing, or optimising electricity demand, they can help match demand and supply, manage peaks and reduce pressure on local networks. This role is becoming increasingly important as electrification accelerates, grid constraints intensify and the need to expand and intensify renewable energy grows.

To understand how for the existing EU regulatory framework enables buildings to act as active assets in a monitoring, informed energy process, research conducted as part of the BlueBird project reviewed national policy implementation in the context of the BlueBird pilot in Spain, Austria, Germany, Poland, Design, the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II), the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), the Energy Communities Directive (ECD), the Energy Storage Directive (ESD) and the Energy Storage Regulation (ESR).

Key takeaways

- 1. National implementation of regulatory foundations for energy sharing, aggregation and citizen participation is emerging but uneven. National progress to secure building as energy flexibility assets occurs at different speeds and in different elements, while remaining incomplete.
- 2. Energy communities, collective self-consumption and aggregation can support building-level and neighborhood-level flexibility, but their practical uptake is still limited by implementation gaps, legal complexity, administrative burdens, restrictive proximity rules and insufficient clarity on the interaction between different frameworks.
- 3. Several enabling practices already exist across the analysed countries, including clean Renewable Energy Community (REC), EED Art. 23 and Citizen Energy Community (CEC), EED Art. 2, 15a frameworks, broader possibilities for collective self-consumption, energy data access arrangements, and more advanced Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), EPBD Art. 15) testing and implementation support. However, to be effective, these elements must be combined systematically into coherent national frameworks.
- 4. Data availability from Distribution System Operators (DSOs) remains a key bottleneck, even where access rights exist. Limited supply, delay, manual procedures or insufficient interoperability continue to restrict energy sharing, storage optimisation and flexibility services.
- 5. The EPBD provides an important enabling layer through the Smart Readiness Indicator, commissioning buildings and EV-ready infrastructure, but these provisions will only translate into system value where they are linked to incentives, digital infrastructure and access to flexibility markets.
- 6. Under the EED, flexibility and energy efficiency are still not systematically treated as alternatives to grid expansion in planning and investment decisions. Capital Expenditure (CapEx)-based incentives, weak coordination and insufficient integration of energy communities into local heating and cooling planning continue to leave progress.

Figure 14. BlueBird Policy Brief

On June 3, 2025 a first public workshop was organized by BPIE for BlueBird as part of the [European Council for an Energy Efficient Economy \(ECEEE\) – Summer Study event](#) (June 1-6, 2026, France). This workshop was organized as an interactive discussion around 3 questions:

1. What is still missing to make building flexibility work in practice? Where do participants see the main barriers along the process of enabling, activating, valorising and verifying building flexibility?
2. Which implementation experiences and good practices can participants share? What lessons can be drawn from research, pilots, policy implementation, market design, energy communities or grid-related work?

3. What should be addressed at EU level in the next policy cycle? Which issues require legislation, guidance, standardisation, implementation support or better coordination between the EPBD, EED, RED and the electricity market framework?

For this workshop a policy brief (in the form of a flyer) and poster were created. ±20 people (academia and industry) attended this workshop.

Figure 15. BlueBird poster at the ECEEE Summer Study event.

Figure 16. BlueBird workshop at ECEEE Summer Study event.

II.10. Outreach to stakeholders

KPI descripton	Target KPI Value	Status
Outreach for surveys / interviews / workshop participation to relevant stakeholders	10000+ users, end industry	11000+ end user participants in surveys; 50+ office workers in pilots in surveys, 20 mixed stakeholders (industry stakeholders, employees, residents) in in-depth focus

	stakeholders, 50+ policy makers	groups, 360+ researchers from academia, 360+ industry stakeholders, 40 policy professionals, 200+ stakeholders from public authorities and cities
# of national and EU policy makers and regulators reached by targeted outreach actions (bilateral meetings, stakeholder meetings, policy events)	150	±40 policy makers reached (int:net and CEAH conferences)
# of policy briefings, factsheets, recommendations	5	1 (policy brief mention in section II.9.
Stakeholder workshops	2 with at least 30 participants	Foreseen in the second half of the project
Webinars to share pilot results with end users	6 in total (1 per pilot, but only 1 for the 2 ENEA pilots combined)	Foreseen for the end of the project

Reaching out to relevant stakeholders is a joint effort between several work packages, especially WP4, WP7 and WP8. Via the WP4 surveys and focus groups, over 11000 end users were questioned and a few industry stakeholders. Via the participation in events, conferences, workshops and fairs (II.7.) and the organization of the public workshop (II.9.), a lot of additional stakeholders were reached (360+ from academia, 360+ from industry, ±40 policy professionals, 200+ people from public authorities, and ±75 additional end users).

To reach national and EU policy makers and regulators a policy brief was created, based on the research reported in deliverable D7.1, and presented and discussed during the workshop that BlueBird hosted as part of the [European Council for an Energy Efficient Economy \(ECEEE\) – Summer Study event](#) (see previous section). In the second half of the project additional stakeholder workshops will be organised and towards the end of the project webinars per pilot will be organized to share the respective obtained results with the involved end users and other relevant stakeholders.

III. ENGAGEMENT WITH EU LEVEL STAKEHOLDERS AND LIAISONS WITH EU INITIATIVES

The main aim of *T8.3 Stakeholder engagement and liaisons with EU initiatives* is to create links with other relevant EU projects and EU initiatives for a continuous knowledge exchange.

As a first action, BlueBird joined the [Smart Energy Cluster](#), a collaboration of more than 40 ongoing EU projects focused on merging different energy services and incorporating non-energy benefits whilst overcoming market fragmentation and fostering cooperation. This initiative, set up by the [InEExS LIFE project](#) (finished last year) wants to bridge gaps and create a common ground for business development across different segments. The main goals are to:

- Communicate the projects' activities and success stories to groups interested in smart energy solutions
- Amplify the impact of innovative service offerings, reduced energy costs for end users
- Achieve faster payback periods for sustainable energy investments

Participation in the Smart Energy Cluster allows us to easier reach out to relevant other projects and participate in joint dissemination events (e.g. the presentation of BlueBird on the final conference of the InEExS LIFE project and the joint application for a session on [Smart City Expo World Congress 2026](#) mentioned higher).

Via this cluster we approached a few projects with similar objectives as BlueBird:

- [CELINE](#): The CELINE project focuses on the design of a Digital Toolbox to optimise energy management and empower consumers in households, energy communities, and cooperative groups. BlueBird partners AIT and CIMNE are also part of this project.
- [EVELIXIA](#): The EVELIXIA project aims to realize buildings as Active Utility Nodes, making the EU building stock more energy efficient, better connected with grids, more flexible by combining occupant needs with utility signals, and smarter in terms of co-optimization of energy efficiency, flexibility and occupant preferences.
- [STUNNED](#): The STUNNED project aims to empower energy communities to become active players in energy flexibility markets, and to reduce the energy consumption of buildings.

We organized a few confcalls with these projects and discussed potential joint dissemination activities on events such as [Enlit Europe](#), [Sustainable Places](#) and [EUSEW](#). We will also further explore the possibility to write a joint white paper on flexibility.

Recently we got in contact with the [ENTRANCE](#) project, BlueBird's sister project within the *HORIZON-CL5-2024-D4-01-02 – Smart Grid Ready Buildings* call. Just like BlueBird, the ENTRANCE project focuses on seamlessly integrating buildings into the energy system and actively engaging end users in the energy market.

We had a first discussion with the ENTRANCE project and this resulted in a number of interesting opportunities for collaboration and joint dissemination, including:

- Joint organization of a policy session on the EU Sustainable Energy Week of 2027.
- Joint presentation on the yearly REHVA summit in Brussels. [REHVA](#) is the communication & dissemination lead of the ENTRANCE project.
- Possible joint participation in some of the events mentioned earlier, such as Sustainable Places and the SmartGreens conference.
- A possible joint publication in the [REHVA European HVAC journal](#).

BlueBird is also active in the [BRIDGE initiative](#). As mentioned in section II.4. , several partners attended the BRIDGE General Assembly on March 25-26 2025 in Brussels where we distributed our project flyer. Furthermore, several partners are active in BRIDGE working groups:

- As part of the BRIDGE Initiative’s Consumer and Citizen Engagement Working Group, the university of Seeburg (SEEBG) actively participated in multiple stakeholder engagement meetings within the “Indicators of Engagement” subgroup. This group focuses on developing common approaches and practical guidance for assessing stakeholder engagement and its impacts across European energy projects. SEEBG contributed behavioral science expertise by delivering a presentation on behavioral indicators of engagement, demonstrating how Horizon projects can complement traditional survey- and interview-based assessments with objective behavioral measures and experimental field-trial approaches. The presentation highlighted opportunities to address common shortcomings in engagement evaluation and improve the measurement of project impacts. In addition, SEEBG presented the empowerment framework developed within the BlueBird project, showcasing how engagement and empowerment can be operationalized and measured in practice. These contributions supported discussions on developing more robust and meaningful engagement indicators that capture changes in capabilities, motivation, and active participation. Beyond workshop participation, SEEBG also contributed to the annual BRIDGE report by authoring a dedicated subsection on behavioral indicators of engagement and empowerment-based assessment approaches. Through these activities, SEEBG supported knowledge exchange across projects and contributed to the development of shared methodologies for evaluating and strengthening citizen and consumer engagement in the European energy transition.
- As part of the BRIDGE Initiative Business Models Working Group, AIT contributed to Task 1, which focuses on developing common methodologies and practical guidance for capturing business ideas, designing business models, and supporting the exploitation of innovation results across European energy projects. We participated in two online co-creation workshops dedicated to value chains and value propositions, working alongside representatives from numerous EU-funded projects. Through structured breakout sessions and plenary discussions, participants jointly analysed how project innovations create value, address stakeholder needs, generate market and societal benefits, and overcome barriers to adoption and scaling. Our contributions helped capture practical experiences from real project contexts and supported the identification of common patterns, challenges, and success factors. The knowledge generated through these workshops is being consolidated into a BRIDGE handbook that aims to provide structured frameworks, shared terminology, and actionable guidance for business model development and exploitation. By actively engaging in this collaborative process, we supported the BRIDGE objective of strengthening knowledge exchange between projects and enabling more robust, replicable, and market-ready business models that can accelerate the uptake of innovative energy solutions across Europe.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Communication & Dissemination activities	Results obtained until M18
Public project website	Project website online since March 2025 featuring regular updates on the research activities, pilot trials, and dissemination & communication activities
Project Zenodo community	Publication of public deliverables, research papers, flyers, posters, presentations, press releases, white paper, etc. on Zenodo with link to the EU Open Research Repository
LinkedIn project page	Set up of LinkedIn project page with currently 216 followers. 31 posts since the start of the project reaching 6312 members and receiving 413 reactions.
Press releases, flyers, posters, white papers	Publication of 2 electronic press releases, creation of 2 project flyers and 2 posters and publication of a first project white paper
Scientific publications	3 workshop papers presented and published, a fourth paper accepted for publication in July and several papers in review or preparation.
Participation in conferences, workshops, fairs and events	BlueBird has been presented 15 times on diverse events, conferences, workshops and fairs reaching 360+ researchers from academia, 360+ industry stakeholders, ±40 policy stakeholders, 200+ stakeholders from public authorities and cities, and ±75 end users. Furthermore a first project public workshop was organized as part of the ECEEE Summer Study event
Outreach to stakeholders	Besides the stakeholders reached via participation in diverse events, over 11000 extra end users were reached (+ a few industry stakeholders) via a large scale survey, and several focus groups (WP4)
Engagement with EU level stakeholders and liaisons with EU initiatives	BlueBird is an active member of the Smart Energy Cluster, uniting over 40 research projects in the energy domain. BlueBird reached out to several of these projects directly, and actively participated in several BRIDGE working groups.

Table 1. Summary of communication and dissemination activities until M18

In conclusion, BlueBird is actively promoting its vision, activities, and emerging results to key stakeholders and the wider public through a diverse portfolio of communication and dissemination channels. These include the project website, LinkedIn, promotional materials such as flyers and posters, press releases, scientific publications, a white paper, and a strong participation in conferences, workshops, fairs, and other relevant events. Table 1 provides a summary of these activities.

As the project progresses into its second half and tangible outcomes from the various work packages and the seven pilot demonstrations become available, communication and dissemination efforts are expected to intensify further.

The project has actively contributed to several BRIDGE working groups and has set up collaborations with other relevant Horizon Europe initiatives, notably through the Smart Energy Cluster. These connections provide valuable opportunities for knowledge exchange, alignment, and impact amplification. During the remainder of the project, these collaborations will be further expanded through joint dissemination activities, including conference and workshop contributions, event participation, and collaborative publications.

